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[Glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitors in the treatment of thromboembolic events related to endovascular treatment of cerebral aneurysms-systematic review and meta-analysis](#)**Abstract:**

BACKGROUND AND AIMS: Thromboembolism complication is considered the most common complication associated with the treatment of endovascular. This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to assess the studies investigating the effect of glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitor agents on thromboembolic complications during endovascular aneurysm coiling. MATERIALS AND METHODS: This systematic review investigated the outcome of the use of three glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitor agents (ie abciximab, tirofiban, and eptifibatide) on the thromboembolic complications during endovascular aneurysm coiling. The electronic databases of PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Medline were searched up to 25 June 2021, using the keywords "Abciximab," "Tirofiban," and "Eptifibatide" in combination with "Thromboembolism Complication," "Aneurysms," and "Endovascular Aneurysm Coiling." RESULTS: A total of 21 articles were found to be eligible and included in this review. The rates of complete and partial recanalization were estimated to be 56% and 92% in patients who underwent abciximab and tirofiban therapy, respectively. Rupture aneurysms were found in the majority of patients. In general, the mortality rate of the patients treated for thromboembolic complications during endovascular treatment of cerebral aneurysms with glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitors was found to be 4.8% (CI 95%:0.027-0.067; $p < .005$). The average remission rate in studies investigating thromboembolism was 91% (CI 95%:0.88-0.95, I(2) : 65.65/ $p < .001$). CONCLUSION: Based on the obtained results, a higher mean rate of complete recanalization by eptifibatide was found in studies in which abciximab or tirofiban were used, compared to other mentioned agents. Moreover, the amount of hemorrhage was reported to be less after using tirofiban rather than abciximab.

Keywords: Abciximab, cerebral aneurysm, eptifibatide, tirofiban

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